

The pedagogical category of physical exercise.

Spatial exercises.

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***Anatatsiya:** in the process of many years of physical training physical exercise, physical education and power factors are used as a means of gigienik sog'lomlashtiruvchi nature. Physical exercise is the main tool of physical education, it historically gymnastics, games, sports and tourism as a tool of the education process in the way groups are separated and has been using. Physical exercise - that is, the requirements of physical education qonuniyat consciously fulfilled the category of voluntary movement is understood to be a variety of activities. The activities of such action gymnastics, games, sports, tourism workout as was historically tizimlashti, balls and usuliyati have been filled.*

Keywords: exercise, gigyenik factors, sog'lomlashtiruvchi the power of nature, exercise technique, basic bo'gin of the technical details, the technical basis.

That man's actions have reached a stage of the integrity of the complex is noted. The action of the integrity of the act, which was founded at the effects of this interaction are mutually associated and will show up in the action; the action of the details of the change as a result of one phase, a number of other details in terms of time, the change will take place. The theory and practice of physical education in the structure of the movement is talking about. The structure of the movement – its of all the components is legally bound as a single whole, we have mutual.

Happens at a certain time in the space of all human action, so the action of spatial, time and space - time characteristics can talk about the structure containing kinematik. Kinematik action with the dynamic structure of the structure, that is, this is determined by the interplay of external and internal forces that cause them to act.

Made another important move in motion a complicated a whole side – side to the rhythm of the action and the allocation of the time of power relations in complex cases, the reflecting side is shown.

The dynamic interaction of structure and action kinematik bound, one of them leads to the change of two legally change.

In doing physical exercise in the context of each specific pedagogical the importance of each of these characteristics will be different. Some of them play the main role in various stages of teaching one of the other time is of secondary importance. However, all the characteristic of action come together in times of physical exercises that may appear technically provides a very straightforward implementation with due regard.

The trajectory of movement of the part's condition gavin and gavin (path) technique is related to the spatial characteristics of physical exercise.

Performing physical exercise at the time of gavin and many of its parts in relation to each other o'zgartiribgina the condition does not remain static tension of the muscles in the photo but arguably at the expense of free will retain her position as inactive.

Many will not depend on the usefulness of physical exercise in many cases only the initial condition, but the condition of its state or action in the whole process of certain parts of certain

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gavin, related also to be in a situation much more useful. For example, the pool's horizontal location, and this reduces the resistance of the external environment to take konki velosipedchi bukchayib allows you to move forward faster with gavin's. Gavin's more than extra work in each of the appointing gavin tramlindan jump down and result in increases the resistance of the air, at the same time move ahead of gavin and this reduces the resistance of the air in the distance with a jump to prolong.

In the process of moving with the change of the direction of change and the same dynamic condition gavin gavin base reactions due to the terms of this direction are comfortable to tezlanish can give. Them running short and long distances, standing jump to the complexity and come from a place beyond the limit gavin ran uzunlikka depsinib be going in a different example cases in phase.

A common condition in some type of physical exercise and gavin is poured into certain parts of the special requirements of the position. Compliance with these requirements biomexanik angles from the goal is not just physical exercise, but the beautiful view of implementation of the action from the point came out too. For example, in figurali konki flying, jump into the water is not only the complexity of the coordination of exercise and gymnastics, but gavin environment of the state as to the accuracy, bold action and freedom, sophistication, and other similar external appearances also taken into account and assessed.

Any action you need to know the trajectory of moving on gavin's part separate. Trajectory at three things: the shape of the trajectory, and the transition amplituda can show the direction of movement.

Linear linear curve type according to the shape of the trajectory and actions can be. Observations of the people make the effort shows that no linear time. Any part of gavin in cases where a short distance you need to move with great speed into (for example, in boxing to give the tattoo on the linear movement of the importance of more. Active movements of the diversity of the shape of the trajectory of a certain consolidation gavin mainly determined by the nerve centre to be part of the development of competence.

Gavin's trajectory also depends on the complexity of the shape of the moving parts; this is how big the part is, its shape is so simple. For example, the number of the pelvis muscles around the joints too much, the location of them are also diverse, but a lot of hand movement, as the movement of the legs and not smart.

The effectiveness of physical exercise workout technique involved the successful implementation of effects on the body show and moving on to gavin, its components or moving parts to give direction on how depends on. The direction of movement in physical education in the practice of either the surface of a body, or external is determined by intentions. For example, the hands forward or side to side unless we are raised, we will determine the direction of hand movement gavin relation of our own. Up-down, forward-back, right-left, the recipe called to the main direction of gavin adopted people.

Amplituda of action – this is the width of the act. Amplituda large-angle is determined by the level of small. General gavin of the zveno movement sometimes a few amplituda linear measure (for example, the step length – 80 cm) or conditional characters (for example, to cho'qqayib half) will identify with. Some of the actions of the joints of the composition of human gavin zveno amplituda, linking the hardware and depends on the elasticity of the muscles.

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The unit of time represents the speed of the mobility of solids in space. The speed that is passed the length of the path is determined by the ratio passed on to the time I spent in the same way. Usually, you define the speed in meters/second is measured. The point is the same in the speed of movement all of you the way if such action the action is flat, it changes you, uneven movement is called. Tezlanish of the change in unit time is called speed.

From the perspective of psychological and methodological allocated to the optimal speed and maximum speed. Sports plays an important role in the speed of action at the technical: how speed is great that is so high sports results.

However, for you to achieve the highest results is often not the maximum speed, but speed is important to the optimal action for every athlete. Speed can be free and compulsory. For example, in the rise of a hill chang'ichi free speed is speed, while tepalikdan shall be binding on down.

How much time his pace and movement characteristic of the time of action continue to be of the expression.

Continue to the condition and movements of the body plays an important role in changes in activity. Total size of downloads, you can edit change both with the duration of exercise performance. At some phase of technical action of physical exercise (rowing and rowing go out the back, wrapped in the throw of removal or movement of some part of the gavin is of great importance. The work carried out, how much time giving information about the last time enhancing the participation of the delegations time to stand increases.

The pace of the action. When the frequency of the recurrence of pace, try a cycle or the amount of movement in the unit of time is understood to be. For example, the pace of our walk – about 120-140 step listened to it, wrapped in pace about rowing – rowing listened wrapped it 30-40 times we will speak.

The pace of the action depends on the weight or part of moving on gavin inersiya moment. For example, a hand moving paws than trying to gavin (1-2 moves per second) much higher rate (per second trying 8-10) you can keep. With the change of pace of the movement is often in terms of quality and also the whole structure will change. For example, the limit increased from you goes a certain pace to walk, if running becomes.

Downloads pedagogical practice in order to enhance or reduce the use of different rates of physiological action.

“Rhythm” is the word is very common, applies to diverse phenomena. From time to time the rhythm of repeated itself consists of. The main terms of the rhythm in this act strong, the moment to highlight any aspects of the change and display the presence of different time interval, the more likely it is to exchange. Thus, the rhythm of movements (complex dynamics-time) is characteristic.

To the rhythm of the movement strong, fulfilled with a special power belongs the part of diverse in terms of time to be in a relationship. Bo'shashtirilishining muscles physical exercise in tension and master the technique of taking accurate and timely exchange of sport that is seen in one of the most important indicators. The rhythm of motion in highly qualified athletes ordinary conditions it is very clear.

Technically perfect action of a certain kind of person do you can see clearly the purpose of each is carried out in accordance with the rhythm. Depending on the individual characteristics of each athlete that his action should be both out of their rhythm.

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The action of doing physical exercise in accordance with the rhythm of the lens qonuniyat technique created by man is rational and regulated.

Gavin the man to the effects of internal and external forces that will affect the movement of power.

Internal forces include the following:

a) the musculoskeletal apparatus of the passive force – elastic strength of the muscles, the muscles of cho'ziluvchanlik and b.;

b) the apparatus and the action of the active force – the power of pull of the muscle;

b) reactive power – up of gavin in the process of the action of the executive power zveno otherwise at the time of connection to each other.

The man on the outside of the power of external forces affecting gavin is called. Physical exercise is the power of outside of doing the following:

a) the weight of gavin in their power;

b) the power base of the reactions;

v) of the external environment (water, air) and physical properties of solids (the opponent in the fight, in partnership akrobatika) the power of resistance to external weights, the power of people who move from place inersion of the solids.

Distributed in accordance with the physical exercise, which constitute a particular action in which the action begins with activities of which one finished with. For the purposes of teaching and research, it is desirable to divide it into the third phase of physical exercise.

Action the system	Running-depsinib to-flight-yto fall to the ground			
trying phase	1	2	3	4
Action part of the	Preparation	of the main		Closing

Depending on the intensity of physical exercise and continue to be the phase of the process you are indicating changes in the body.

SIQDI - CHTO - sports the ability to work in the dynamics of fatigue and recovery.

FF - some active functional dynamics of the body systems.

BMS - bioenergetik and spend the dynamics of the recovery of substances.

SS - superkompensatsiya effectiveness.

The importance of the preparation phase is to create the most favorable conditions for the implementation of the action in the main phase. For example, to go running in the preparation phase is rushed and jumped in.

Jump from place to bend your legs and pushing hands before doing so finds depsinib rocking to the phase of whom is from the main action, with his help, the main function of the movement is removed. For example, jump from place to depsinib to fly.

The main action is aimed at solving immediate action in the main phase of the task. Biodynamic driving force in the appropriate place in context the most important thing in this phase is in the direction of at the moment is to use appropriate and necessary. For example, the method

of doing so in hand in the pool with the secretary finds time to lift from the water and the waves moving from whom gavin previously active will cause you to appear.

In the last phase of the movement is completed, imaginative words, in this phase, working out of the situation allows. This jump include inlanding on the ground, dash is running a bit after you finish

The main phase of action which constitute the basis of the technique, with the help of the organization, while the remaining two phase, the details of the technique is carried out with the help of the executive action.

In the category of physical exercise to be linked to each other in accordance with the character of this most important of them distribution to the group. With the help of the teacher will determine the features of physical exercise category, consequently, exercise to select Lightemergency will this meet the requirements of the pedagogical task. As long as advancing the science of physical education, since it is continuous is enriched with new information, does not always remain the same category in a while.

Every workout is not one, but a few specific character. Shcan be represented exactly the same in the same category for her every workout. For example, to draw on the anatomical characters (hands and muscles for exercise) is also in the category, basically, the quality of the action (more power) reflect the development of the in that category will show up. Consequently, unsuitable for any condition, can not be created from a single category; the category of pedagogical tasks for withdrawals, you need to take into account the most significant signs.

Historically composed of the system of physical education on the symptoms of the content to the category of physical exercise (gymnastics, games, tourism, sport) is. This category into five groups are distributed on physical exercise.

1. Gymnastic exercises were created artificially in the activity characterize the diversity of action, their effectiveness to the body, the influence of its composition, as well as the combination is determined by the complexity and the coordination of all the action.

Sog'lomlashtiruvchi content types composed from action play exercises (running, to throw and so on.k.) game is made in conformity with the situation changing in different variants and in general on the effectiveness of exposure to the organism and the action will be evaluated on the ultimate result.

Travel workouts in walking, running, jumping, overcoming obstacles in each extra walking, cycling, walking, swimming and others in the boat included.

Sog'lomlashtiruvchi conditions for walking, running and jumping to overcome obstacles, each extra walking, cycling, walking, rowing the boat and wrapped with added, organizes travel for a workout. Complex influence of their effectiveness to the organism to cope with the results of the distance and the barriers in place will be evaluated.

Sports sport exercise to achieve maximum results for ixtisoslash subject to and in compliance with the standardized artificial sports category only the last group, are noted them appropriate if the characters of the first three can be included in the group (sports gymnastics workout, exercise and sports games, sports travel is an exercise).

The descriptive character of this category of exercise seems to be shartilik variations in this group. So, for example running, though expressed in different variants to'rttala group, even if just a general mo'ljali given in a similar category of physical exercises.

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2. Signs of muscle activity issued on exercise of the category (on the character of influencing the development of the quality of the action).

Speed-strength exercises will require you to make the maximum effort involved in a relatively short time (for example: short-distance running, jump review); to show durability, which requires physical exercise (e.g., running long distances, each extra walk, etc.).

Give regular exchange of excellent reference level according to changing conditions, driving to show the quality of which requires a set of physical exercises (games, tete-a-tete fight). This category shartlilik on the one hand, allows you to choose the physical exercise. With his help you can achieve the effective development of the quality of the movement. On the second hand, this is what he is know to have the quality necessary to successfully complete the exercise of which or featured.

3. Ilmiylik function of the category of physical exercise on their importance for withdrawals. This category will shartlilik iboratki, in which movement of skills, skills formation and movement will be allocated on the basis of the quality of exercise aimed at the development of artificial, ajralmasdir process both at the same time. However, the major practical meaning of such a category does not lose. Exercise it to teach the tasks in each stage of maturity on many levels and will help you to choose to take off, leading them to take off assist.

4. Basically the character of physical exercise on the development of certain muscle groups category: belt of the neck muscles and the muscles in the hands for gavin to yelka, waist and leg muscles are provided. Boldir exercises in this category-the muscle for the heel, laptop etc for the muscle to stand erect, sit, lay, and if the individual pairs with the subject, and the subject is used for the development of the quality fulfilled without exercise physical exercises.

5. Physical exercise on the category of sports.

Have exercise specific to the category of each type of sport. Biomexanika provide in addition to teaching in the category (static, dynamic, cycle, atsiklli, and other exercise kombinatsiyalashtirilgan) to exercise physiologist with different power while in (maximum, submaksimal, and big mo‘, with a capacity of drake passage to the south) to be taken to exercise fulfilled.

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